

Mycelium-based biocomposites from recycled wood: influence of fungal species on properties of biocomposites

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ABSTRACT

Mycelium-based bio-composites (MBB) are composite materials that are produced by the growth of fungal mycelia on the substrate from lignocellulosic (LC) materials such as straw, husks or wood particles. Adhesives are not used in this technology to produce composites, because the LC particles are bonded by mycelium. MBB can be used for packaging, decorative design objects or for furniture. In the presented research particles from recycled wood were used to produce not-pressed MBB. *Ganoderma lucidum*, *Ganoderma lingzhi* and *Pleurotus ostreatus* were selected to grow the MBB from recycled wood. Tensile strength perpendicular to the plane of the board (internal bonding) and moisture uptake of the produced variants of MBB as well as fungi growth rate were evaluated. It was observed that all used fungal species were able to fully colonise the substrate from recycled wood and that the contaminants present in the recycled wood did not negatively affect the ability of fungi to colonise the substrate. Produced MBB reached promising properties that offer the possibility of using the developed material for thermal insulation purposes.

Key words: bio-composite, cellulose, heat insulation, mycelium, recycled wood

1. INTRODUCTION

The need to reduce production from traditional materials based on non-renewable resources goes hand in hand with the demand for circular production. Two types of materials, plastics and wood-based composites, have become the most used in furniture production in recent decades. However, the current production and disposal of plastics pose a social threat. In producing particleboards and MDF boards, synthetic resins are used as binders. These resins often contain formaldehyde, a volatile organic compound (VOC). Although both materials can be recycled to some extent, the presence of synthetic resins makes the recycling process more difficult and limited. Mycelium-based biocomposites (MBB) are considered promising ecologically sustainable alternative synthetic materials. They use waste from organic farming and woodworking. The key advantages of the resulting MBB are the low cost of raw materials, rapid biodegradability, recycling and a minimal carbon footprint (Dias et al., 2021).

MBBs are created on the principle of the growth of a saprophyte fungus. The mycelium connects the particles of the nutrient substrate through a 3D network of hyphae. As a substrate, various secondary agricultural and forestry wastes rich in cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin are used (Butu et al., 2020). MBB is grown on lignocellulosic substrates without the addition of adhesives or harmful waste generation (Elsacker et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2021). MBBs offer a range of uses that depend on the properties given by the main factors, i.e. by the choice of fungi and lignocellulosic substrate, their interaction, growth conditions and processing techniques (Sydor et al., 2021).

The binder of MBB is the mycelium of wood-decaying fungi, in which structurally chitin predominates, complemented by β -glucans and glycoproteins (Shen et al., 2023). The

mycelium grows into a three-dimensional network of filamentous long hyphae approximately 2 to 20 μm in diameter that form the vegetative part of the fungi (Fricker et al., 2007). Hyphae attach lignocellulosic particles to each other by breaking down polymers of cellulose, hemicelluloses, lignin and other sugars from their substrate into smaller molecules by secreting enzymes. The mycelium on the surface forms a compact layer, referred to as fungal skin (Yang et al., 2021; Aiduang et al., 2022a).

Studies indicate the choice of fungus as an essential factor for future material properties (Appels et al., 2019). The required criteria for the selection of mycelium are the growth rate, resistance to contamination, undemanding to growth conditions, especially temperature and humidity, the hyphal system and the type fungus. Based on studies with the published name of the fungal species, the most suitable in terms of MBB formation is the *Pleurotus* genus with 25.0%, followed by *Ganoderma* (22.2%), *Trametes* (18.1%), *Pycnoporus* (4.2%), *Polyporus* (2.8%), *Agaricus* (2.8%), *Coriolus* (2.8%) and *Lentinula* (2.8%) (Aiduang et al., 2022a; Cerimi et al., 2019).

In summary, lignocellulosic residues from agricultural and woodworking production are used for the production of MBB (Javadian et al., 2020). The substrate can be sawdust, shavings, chips, shavings, straw and other waste materials such as cardboard, coffee waste, oat bran, hemp fibres, cotton, coconut fibres, rapeseed straw fibres, reed fibres, raw cellulose (from sewage treatment), flax fibers, wood chips, sorghum, husks, elephant grass, *Miscanthus* (Dias et al., 2021). Shavings and sawdust from beech wood, together with cardboard and wood chips, appear to be a potential material for the formation of MBB (Vašatko et al., 2022). An ideal substrate for fungal growth should provide nutrients such as carbon, nitrogen, minerals and water (Beck et al., 2018). The composition, character and properties of the substrate affect the ability of fungi to grow and are a key factor in the resulting physical and mechanical properties of MBB (Jones et al., 2020). Cellulose and lignin are essential for mycelial growth, they are the components that give MBB stiffness and strength (Yang et al., 2021). Cellulose is used by the mycelium for its growth, cellulose molecules are in the mycelium assembled into long bundles of microfibrils. In many studies, the substrate was supplemented with a substance containing simple sugars and minerals, to provide energy for mycelial growth. Rice bran, wheat flour (Vidholdova et al., 2019), calcium carbonate, calcium or sodium sulfate (Aiduang et al., 2022a), potato starch (Dias et al., 2021), cellulose (Vašatko et al., 2022), coffee grounds (Soh and Le Ferrand, 2022), wheat grains, millet, gypsum and others (Shen et al., 2023). The resulting MBB properties also depend on the properties of the substrate and the size of the particles used. Particles of approximately 5-30 mm in size have been reported in studies (Aiduang et al., 2022b; Elsacker et al., 2019; Vašatko et al., 2022). A larger fraction of the substrate leads to stronger MBB but at the same time, too large particles cause slow growth of the fungus. Fine sawdust and dust lead to clumping of parts and impair oxygen distribution (Elsacker et al., 2019).

The presented study aims to produce MBBs from recycled wood (RW) avoiding using valuable agricultural rests and to determine the effect of fungal species on the properties of MBB from RW.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Three fungi species were used to produce composites from recycled wood (RW), namely *Ganoderma lucidum* (VURV-F 5275, Crop Research Institute, Czech Republic), *Ganoderma lingzhi* (M9724, Mycelia, Belgium) and *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Ivory, Sylvan, USA). Grain spawn was used as inoculum. Wheat grains with the addition of gypsum were hydrated (47 \pm 2 % moisture content), sterilised and inoculated by fungi species. The inoculum was 10 days incubated in glass bottles at a temperature of 24°C.

2.2. MBB production

Composites were produced by mycelia growth on substrate from recycled wood. Recycled wood was obtained from Kronospan CR company, and particles initially intended to be used in the middle layer of particleboards were used. The substrates were hydrated to reach the absolute moisture of 60% and were inoculated with prepared inoculum. The inoculation rate was 10% (wet weight/wet weight). Inoculated substrates were climatised at a temperature of 24 °C and relative humidity (RH) 95 %. After 14 days the substrates were fully colonised by fungi, were manually shredded, and filled into cube forms with a side dimension of 50 mm. For heat insulation properties measurement, cylindrical samples with a diameter of 100 mm and height of 70 mm were produced. The composites grew in forms for eight days at a temperature of 24 °C and RH 95%. After this period, samples (examples are depicted in Figure 1) were removed from forms, and the fungi growth was ended by composite drying at a temperature of 103°C for 5 hours.

To quantify the growth rate of individual fungi species on RW, a growth rate test was performed. Hydrated and sterilised RW substrate at an amount of 75 g was filled into glass test tubes with dimensions of 40 mm in diameter and 240 mm in length. The test tubes filled with substrates were inoculated by laying 4 g of inoculum on the top, the test was conducted vertically. Four test tubes were prepared from each variant, and growth increments were marked every three days.

Figure 1. Produced specimens of MBB, from the left *P. ostreatus*, *G. lingzhi* and *G. lucidum*

2.3. MBB properties estimation

The growth rate test was evaluated by measuring increments of mycelium on RW, every tube was measured in three places. The daily increments were presented graphically, and the growth rate was calculated as follows:

$$GR = \frac{l}{t} \quad (1)$$

GR – Growth rate in mm/day

l – Total length of colonised substrate in mm

t – Total time of substrate colonisation in days

Tensile strength perpendicular to the plane of the board (internal bonding) was measured using a TIRAtest 2850 universal testing machine. The method was adopted from EN 319:1993. A total of 10 samples from each variant were measured, and internal bonding was calculated as follows:

$$IB = \frac{F_{max}}{a \cdot b} \quad (2)$$

IB – Internal bonding in MPa

F_{max} – Maximal force applied to the sample in N

a, b – Area dimensions of the test specimen in mm

Water uptake was measured based on EN 1609:2013. Shortly, after weighing the oven-dried samples, the samples were placed in a test tank on a grid that allowed water to pass through. After 24 h submersion in water, the samples were removed from the tank and for 10 minutes placed on a grid that was at an inclination angle of 35°–40°, and after that, the samples were weighted. Water uptake per dry mass of board was calculated as follows:

$$W = \frac{m_{24} - m_0}{m_0} \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

W – Water uptake per dry mass of board in %

m_{24} – Weight of the sample after 24 h water submersion in kg

m_0 – Weight of the oven-dried sample in kg

The analysis of variance was employed to determine whether any of the pairwise differences of the measured properties were statistically significant, and software Statistica12 was used. The Tukey posthoc test was performed to determine significant differences between group means.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results clearly show that all three used fungal species are able to colonize substrate from RW particles, the results of the growth test are depicted in Figure 2 and the calculated values of growth rate are presented in Table 1. The highest growth rate was reached by *G. lingzhi* was 4.9 mm/day, *P. ostreatus* reached 4.8 mm/day, the difference between the means is not statistically significant. *G. lucidum* reached the lowest growth rate, however the lower growth rate did not negatively affect the properties of produced MBB.

Figure 2. Influence of fungus on growth rate

Table 1. Growth rate results

Fungus	Growth rate (mm/day)	Standard deviation (mm/day)
<i>G. lucidum</i>	1.9	0.4
<i>G. lingzhi</i>	4.9	0.1
<i>P. ostreatus</i>	4.8	0.3

Density significantly affects the properties of wood-based materials and therefore density of produced MBB was monitored. The density of produced MBB is listed in Table 2, the target density was 150 kg/m³, however, due to manual production, small variations occurred. MBB produced using *P. ostreatus* reached a lower density than the other two MBB variants which is caused mainly due to falling out of particles from the *P. ostreatus* MBB variant during MBB removal from forms. This phenomenon of missing particles in the surface layer of MBB can be seen in Figure 1.

Table 2. Density of produced MBB

Fungus	Density (kg/m ³)	Standard deviation (kg/m ³)
<i>G. lucidum</i>	155.9	5.7
<i>G. lingzhi</i>	154.1	2.9
<i>P. ostreatus</i>	144.6	6.8

Note: Density of oven dry MBB

All produced MBB reached low internal bonding. The overall low internal bonding values are caused by the short time of the growing phase during MBB production process. It was already reported that a longer time of MBB growing phase significantly improves mechanical properties of the final MBB (Elsacker et al., 2019; Sydor et al., 2021). MBB produced using *G. lingzhi* reached the highest internal bonding, the difference between *G. lingzhi* and *G. lucidum* is statistically significant at the significance level of 0.05. Except for time of growth, internal bonding can be further improved by different substrate composition, substrate moisture and fungal species used (Aiduang et al., 2022b; Elsacker et al., 2019; Vařatko et al., 2022).

Figure 3. Influence of fungus on internal bonding of MBB

The developed MBB exhibited 24 h water uptake in the range from 85% to 163%. MBB produced using *G. lingzhi* and *G. lucidum* exhibited lower water uptake which was caused by fungal skin grown on the surface of MBB. *P. ostreatus* did not form fungal skin on the surface of the samples and therefore water was allowed to fully penetrate the samples. The results of 24 h water uptake can be seen on the Figure 4. Greater thickness of fungal skin could even further decrease the 24 h water uptake. The higher thickness of fungal skin can be achieved by an additional MBB growing phase after MBB removal from the forms (Elsacker et al., 2019).

Figure 4. Influence of fungus on water uptake of MBB

4. CONCLUSIONS

The presented paper presents a development of MBB from recycled wood produced using three different fungal species, namely *G. lingzhi*, *G. lucidum* and *P. ostreatus*. The results clearly show that all three used fungal species are able to colonize substrate from RW particles. Produced MBB showed low internal bonding which was caused by a short growing phase during the MBB production. It was observed that *G. lingzhi* and *G. lucidum* were able to form a fungal skin on the surface of samples which enhanced the water uptake. *G. lucidum* exhibited a lower growth rate which negatively influenced the internal bonding of produced MBB but did not negatively influence 24 h water uptake.

Thanks to the low density and internal bonding of MBB, the results indicated that the produced MBB can be considered only for utilisation for heat insulation properties. However, the methodology of MBB production will be further optimised and it is expected that both the physical and mechanical properties of MBB from RW particles can be substantially improved.

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by HORIZON-MSCA-2022-PF-01-01, project number: 101105443, project acronym: LignoMBB.

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